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Recommendations on Data Licensing

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1 Introduction

It is crucial to license your data when conducting research. Digital information is governed by copyright laws, and without a clear context, it is uncertain whether others can use your data. By providing a license, you automate the process of seeking permission, which benefits both the giver and the receiver. However, it is important to note that in some countries, such as Germany, it is not possible to waive one's copyright. Data that lack a suitable open license cannot be considered open. A license offers legal clarity for data usage, ensuring that both parties are protected. When selecting a license, it is advisable to choose an established one that addresses questionable edge cases and offers unambiguous terms.

The Open Knowledge Foundation¹ defines open data and content as "freely used, modified, and shared by anyone for any purpose."² This means that open data licenses grant users the four fundamental freedoms originally defined for free software:³

- The freedom to run the program for any purpose
- The freedom to study how the program works and modify it as needed, which requires access to the source code.
- The freedom to distribute copies to others and help them.
- The freedom to distribute modified copies to others.

These freedoms can also be applied to open data, allowing users to freely use, analyse, share, and modify the data. The main difference between open data licenses and free or open-source software licenses lies in the obligations that must be met to obtain these rights.

There are already established lists of open source licenses that ensure the four freedoms, such as the list provided by the Open Source Initiative (OSI). However, it is essential to understand the specific characteristics of each license to determine which one is best suited for your data.

¹<https://okfn.org/>

²<https://opendefinition.org/>

³https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/The_Free_Software_Definition#The_Four_Essential_Freedoms_of_Free_Software

2 Licence Types

The field of information technology has a wide variety of licenses that cover different materials and domains. Some licenses apply to multiple domains, such as software, data, and content, while others are domain-specific. This chapter provides an overview of existing and commonly used open data licenses.

It is important to note that there are different definitions of terms such as "free," "open," "libre," and what constitutes "open science data." Therefore, it is essential to understand the specific characteristics of each license to determine which one is best suited for your data.

The most widely recognized open data licenses are the Creative Commons licenses. These licenses provide a flexible and standardized way of sharing content, data, and software. They allow the creators to retain their copyright while allowing others to use, distribute, and modify their work, subject to certain conditions. Another common open data license is the Open Data Commons (ODC) licenses. These licenses provide legal tools for open data sharing, reuse, and distribution, and they have been designed to address the unique challenges of open data. The ODC licenses have been categorized into three types: the Public Domain Dedication and License (PDDL), the Attribution License (ODC-BY), and the Open Database License (ODbL).

Additionally, some domain-specific licenses exist. For instance, the Open Source Initiative (OSI) defines the criteria for software licenses that can be considered open source. These licenses aim to ensure that software can be freely used, modified, and distributed by anyone. In summary, understanding the different license types and their specific characteristics is essential when sharing data, content, or software. By selecting an appropriate license, you can ensure that your work is used and distributed as intended, while retaining your rights as a creator.

2.1 Licenses which are not open

There are certain obligations that a license may formalise, which will prevent the data from being considered open! The Open Knowledge Foundation has a section on non-conformant clauses. In brief, the main relevant clauses are:

- **Non-commercial (NC)**

You may not use the material for commercial purposes. As there is no definition of what is considered commercial, and an NGO or a nonprofit organization may also be considered commercial entities, this clause renders data licensed under it not open.

- **No Derivatives (ND)**

You may not alter, transform, or build upon this work. This limits your

freedom to modify the data and is therefore not open.

3 Open Data Licenses

The open data licenses below are grouped by the three main obligations. For a broader list of licenses, also see: <https://github.com/ifrOSS/ifrOSS/blob/master/OpenDataLicenses.md> and <https://opendefinition.org/licenses/>.

3.1 Public Domain

The public domain is a concept where no copyright or other protections, such as patents and trademarks, exist, thereby imposing no obligations. It is beneficial to have information that clearly indicates and communicates when something is in the public domain. However, in certain countries like Germany, it is not possible to waive one's copyright. To achieve a legal status equivalent to the public domain worldwide, it is recommended to explicitly declare an unrestrictive open license.

For more information, you can refer to the **international definition of public domain**¹.

Understanding the concept of **Gemeinfreiheit** in Germany and Europe is crucial for comprehending the legal aspects of the public domain².

Usecase: Data that does not require attribution to authors, such as "helper tables" for conversions.

Openness: As open as possible, allows to create non-open derivatives.

List of licenses:

ID (SPDX)	Name of license	Comment
CC0-1.0	Creative Commons Zero v1.0	recommended
PDDL-1.0	Open Data Commons Public Domain Dedication and License v1.0	recommended
dl-de/zero-2-0	German Open Data License (German: Datenlizenz Deutschland - Zero - Version 2.0)	granted only by German government
CC-PDDC	Creative Commons Public Domain Certification	not recommended for data

¹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Public_domain

²<https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gemeinfreiheit>

3.2 Attribution

This obligation prescribes creating and placing an attribution string close to the created work. The string must contain the name of the author and/or copyright holder and has sometimes additional requirements, such as a link to the license text or the original source. Be aware that this attribution string is different from the scientific citation string, which is necessary for good scientific practice. Licenses that merely require an attribution are often referred to as permissive licenses

For more information, see [best practices](#) for attribution and [Lizenzhinweis-generator](#)³.

Usecase: Data for which naming of the authors and/or copyright holders is required, e.g. "input and result data". Note: The holder of database rights under EU law is the investor, not the author. The same is true for works made for hire in the US.

Openness: Open and suitable for academic work.

List of licenses:

ID (SPDX)	Name of license	Comment
CC-BY-4.0	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	recommended
ODC-By-1.0	Open Data Commons Attribution License v1.0	recommended
dl-de/zero-2-0	German Open Data License (German: Datenlizenz Deutschland - Zero - Version 2.0)	granted only by German government
CC-PDDC	Creative Commons Public Domain Certification	not recommended for data

3.3 Share-Alike (Copyleft)

The Share-Alike obligation requires that you choose the exact same license for aggregated or modified data. It can be described as reciprocal, hereditary or (negatively connotated) virulent.

For more information see [copyleft](#) on Wikipedia⁴.

Note that different copyleft licenses are incompatible by default! Compatibility among copyleft licenses requires a specific compatibility clause, otherwise they create data silos. The OEP decided for the ODbL as only suitable copyleft license due to the use of OpenStreetMap (OSM) data.

Usecase: Data where naming of the authors is required and all further updates must be open as well, e.g. "manual collection of technical parameters from

³<https://lizenzhinweisgenerator.de/>

⁴<https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Copyleft>

factsheets”.

Openness: Open and will be open forever.

4 Application in OEMetadata

The OEMetadata Standard is based on the Frictionless Data Package Specifications¹. The license for a resource (table or datapackage) is specified by three fields:

- **name:** The name MUST be an Open Definition license ID (SPDX)²
- **path:** A url-or-path (string, that is a fully qualified HTTP address, or a relative POSIX path)
- **title:** A human-readable title of the license

More details on applying licenses can be found in the Frictionless Data blog post³. In addition, two useful keys are included in the metadata to simplify reuse and legal understanding:

- **instruction:** A short description of rights and restrictions. The use of tldrLegal⁴ is recommended. Example: You are free to share and change, but you must attribute, and share derivations under the same license. See for further information.
- **attribution:** The copyright owner of the data. If attribution licenses are used, that name must be acknowledged. Example: © Reiner Lemoine Institut

The license is included as an array (list) by default. This allows dual licensing.

¹<https://frictionlessdata.io/>

²<https://spdx.org/licenses/>

³<https://frictionlessdata.io/blog/2018/03/27/applying-licenses/>

⁴[https://tldrlegal.com/license/odc-open-database-license-\(odbl\)](https://tldrlegal.com/license/odc-open-database-license-(odbl))

5 Licensing in practice

In practice, licensing plays a crucial role in the use of open data, ensuring proper attribution, legal compliance, and enabling the freedom to share and modify data. The OEMetadata standard recognises the significance of licenses in open data and provides a structured approach for documenting license information.

Research and documentation of license information within the OEMetadata standard offers several benefits. Firstly, it facilitates transparency by clearly stating the permissions and restrictions associated with the data. By specifying the license name, path, and title, users can easily understand the terms under which the data can be used, modified, and distributed.

5.1 Using Open Data

Within the OEMetadata string, it is essential to gather and store comprehensive license information alongside the data. Additionally, it is recommended to include an additional entry in the contributions section to document the provenance of the data, ensuring traceability and transparency. When republishing or visualizing the data, it is crucial to create a proper attribution string based on the provided information. Typically, the attribution string should contain the following elements:

- **Title:** Include the title or name of the dataset, providing a clear and concise description of its content.
- **Source:** Specify the source from which the data originated, indicating the repository, website, or platform where it was obtained. A link to the source of the data can be a URL or DOI or persistent ID.
- **Author / Copyright holder:** Acknowledge the individual or organisation that holds the copyright or is the primary creator of the data. The information from **attribution**.
- **Author link:** A link to the homepage.
- **License:** Clearly state the license under which the data is released, ensuring compliance with its terms and conditions. Name and identifier of the license.
- **License link:** A link to the license text.

A suitable format is:

"**Title**"[*Source*] © *Author*[*Author link*] — *License*[*License link*]

An example is:

"**MaStR - Marktstammdatenregister**" © Bundesnetzagentur für Elektrizität, Gas, Telekommunikation, Post und Eisenbahnen — [Datenlizenz Deutschland – Namensnennung – Version 2.0 \(DL-DE-BY-2.0\)](#)

5.2 Using protected data and data without licenses

The use of non-open data has been a topic of increasing importance. While open data initiatives have gained momentum globally, there remains a significant amount of data that is freely accessible on the internet or published somewhere else. Non-open data refers to datasets that are publicly available but have restrictions on usage, or require specific permissions for access.

Non-open data sources can include government databases, proprietary datasets held by private companies, academic research data, and sensitive information such as personal or confidential data. These datasets often contain valuable information that can contribute to research, analysis, policy-making, and decision-making processes. The utilisation of non-open data presents unique challenges and considerations. Access to these datasets may be limited due to legal, privacy, or commercial reasons. Researchers and data practitioners need to navigate licensing agreements, contact the copyright holders, negotiate data-sharing agreements, and comply with data protection regulations to gain access to non-open data.

In Germany, the *Gesetz über Urheberrecht und verwandte Schutzrechte (UrhG)*¹ contains the paragraph § 60c *Wissenschaftliche Forschung* (Copyright Act, § 60c Scientific Research)² that provides provisions specifically for non-commercial scientific research. According to this law:

- (1) Up to 15 percent of a work may be reproduced, distributed, and made publicly accessible for the purpose of non-commercial scientific research. This can be done for a specific group of individuals conducting their own scientific research, as well as for individual third parties for the purpose of assessing the quality of scientific research.
- (2) Up to 75 percent of a work may be reproduced for one's own scientific research.
- (3) Exceptions to paragraphs 1 and 2 apply for illustrations, individual contributions from the same professional or scientific journal, other works of minor extent, and out-of-print works, which can be used in their entirety.

Regarding non-open data, the application of § 60c depends on the specific circumstances and licensing agreements associated with the non-open datasets. Researchers and data practitioners must ensure that they comply with copyright laws, licensing agreements, and any applicable data protection regulations when accessing and using non-open data for scientific research. The provisions may provide some flexibility in reproducing and utilising copyrighted materials within the context of non-commercial scientific research, but the specific permissions and limitations for non-open data should be carefully reviewed and adhered to.

In conclusion, while open data initiatives have made significant progress, the use of non-open data remains a reality. Overcoming the challenges associated

¹<https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/urhg>

²https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/urhg/_60c.html

with non-open data requires collaboration, adherence to ethical and legal standards, and a concerted effort to promote transparency and data sharing. By addressing these issues, researchers and data practitioners can harness the full potential of both open and non-open data sources to drive innovation, enhance decision-making, and foster societal progress.

5.3 Select and apply a license for data

When selecting a suitable open license for data, several considerations come into play. Legal implications and jurisdiction-specific regulations should also be taken into account. Different countries may have their own legal frameworks governing open data licenses, so it is important to ensure compliance with relevant laws. It is important to choose a license that aligns with the principles of open data, promoting accessibility, reuse, and collaboration. The choice of license should reflect the intended type of material (software, data, artwork) and the desired obligations, if any, on data usage. Some licenses may require attribution, ensuring proper credit is given to the original data creators and copyright holder. Some licenses require that you choose the exact same license for aggregated or modified data. It can be described as reciprocal, hereditary or (negatively connotated) virulent.

Table of license types:

	License		
	Public Domain	Attribution	Share-Alike
Openness	As open as possible, but others can create non-open derivatives of it.	Open and suitable for academic work.	Open and will be open forever.
Use-Case	Data for which no attribution to authors is required, e.g. "helper tables" for conversions.	Data for which naming of the authors and/or copyright holders is required, e.g. "input and result data".	Data where all further updates must be open as well, e.g. "manual collection of parameters from factsheets".
Example	Creative Commons Zero v1.0 Universal (CC0)	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC-BY-4.0)	ODC Open Database License v1.0 (ODbL-1.0)

Once a license is chosen, it is essential to properly apply and document the license information. This can be done by including the license statement and relevant details within the data documentation and metadata. The license information should clearly state the terms and conditions under which the data is made available, including any requirements for attribution, modifications, and redistribution.

6 Licence compatibility

Ensuring licence compatibility between various different licences is usually a challenging manual task. The auditor should have a sound understanding of legal concepts and its subtle nuances.

dalicc

DALICC ("Data Licenses Clearance Center")¹ is an EU-funded research project aimed at developing a platform and tools to support the identification, clearance, and management of data licenses. The project's goal is to address the challenges surrounding data licensing in order to foster data interoperability, reuse, and sharing while ensuring legal compliance.

The DALICC project focuses on developing innovative technologies and methodologies to automate and streamline the process of understanding and managing data licenses. It aims to provide a comprehensive framework for organisations and individuals to identify the licenses applicable to their data, analyse the rights and restrictions associated with those licenses, and manage compliance accordingly.

The platform integrates legal knowledge and natural language processing techniques to interpret and analyse license texts, allowing users to obtain a better understanding of the rights and obligations associated with data licenses. It also provides functionalities for assessing license compatibility, automating clearance processes, and facilitating data sharing within legal boundaries.

Overall, the DALICC project aims to address the complex landscape of data licensing by providing tools and solutions that simplify the identification, clear-

¹<https://docs.dalicc.net/>

Table 6.1: Compatibility matrix of database licences with each other in case that two data sets are used and mixed. The table is invariant to transposition. The green colour indicates full compatibility and red incompatibility. Public domain is a special case, as often hidden additional hidden additional agreements apply.

Final license Original license	CC0 Public Domain	CC-BY-4.0	dl-de/by-2-0	ODbL-1.0	CC-BY-SA-4.0
CC0 PublicDomain					
CC-BY-4.0					
dl-de/by-2-0					
ODbL-1.0					
CC-BYSA-4.0					

ance, and management of licenses, promoting data interoperability, and facilitating legal compliance in data-driven environments.

The first component makes a reference to the ODRL information model² to express permissions, duties and prohibitions stated in a license. It uses vocabularies from ODRL, CCRel and particular extensions to describe licenses for machine processing in a legally valid manner. In this respect a license can be understood as a policy that defines specific actions as permissions, duties or prohibitions.

The second component is the so-called Dependency Graph. This graph expresses the valid relationships between various actions defined in a license. The graph currently consists of three basic relationships: “included in”, “implies” and “contradicts”. The graph is used to check the consistency of the license itself and to detect potential conflicts arising from contradicting actions defined in two or more licenses.

²<https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/>

7 Questions section

7.1 Beginner

(Question) **What is an open licence?**

(Answer) An open license, also known as an open-source license or open content license, is a legal agreement that grants specific permissions to users to use, modify, distribute, and share a particular work or content. It is commonly associated with software, but it can also apply to various types of creative works, such as text, images, music, and more.

The primary purpose of an open license is to promote the principles of openness, collaboration, and free sharing of knowledge and creativity. Open licenses enable individuals or organizations to make their works freely available to others, allowing them to use, adapt, and build upon the original work without extensive legal restrictions or the need to seek explicit permission.

Open licenses typically include terms and conditions that outline the rights and responsibilities of the licensees (users) and licensors (creators). While the specific terms may vary depending on the chosen open license, some common characteristics include:

Permissive Use: Open licenses allow users to use the licensed work for various purposes, whether it's personal, commercial, educational, or non-profit.

Modification: Open licenses often permit users to modify the licensed work, allowing them to adapt it to their specific needs or improve upon the original.

Distribution: Open licenses generally allow users to distribute copies of the licensed work to others, ensuring the broad availability of the content.

Attribution: Many open licenses require proper attribution to the original creator(s) of the work, acknowledging their contribution.

Share-Alike: Some open licenses, such as the Creative Commons Share-Alike licenses, mandate that derivative works be released under the same or a compatible open license, ensuring that the openness and freedom of the work are preserved in subsequent versions.

It's important to note that open licenses do not mean that the work is devoid of any copyright or intellectual property protections. Instead, they provide a framework for licensing and sharing intellectual property in a more open and collaborative manner while still respecting the rights of the original creator(s).

(Question) When do I need to licence my artefacts?

(Answer) In general, licensing your artifacts provides clarity on the permissions and restrictions associated with their use, promotes collaboration, and allows others to benefit from your work while respecting your rights as the creator. It's important to choose a license that aligns with your intentions and goals, whether it's maximizing openness, protecting your work, or striking a balance between the two. Consulting legal professionals or exploring established open licenses can help you make informed decisions regarding licensing your artifacts.

(Question) Why should I licence my artefact?

(Answer) It's important to note that the specific reasons for licensing your artifact may vary depending on your goals, the type of artifact, and the context in which it will be used. Carefully selecting an appropriate license can help you achieve your desired outcomes and strike a balance between protecting your rights and encouraging the desired use and dissemination of your artifact.

There are several reasons why licensing your artifact can be beneficial:

- a) **Protection:** By licensing your artifact, you establish legal rights and protections for your work. Copyright law automatically grants you certain exclusive rights as the creator, but a license can clearly outline the permissions and restrictions you want to apply. This helps prevent others from using your artifact in ways that may infringe on your rights or misrepresent your work.
- b) **Control:** Licensing allows you to maintain control over how your artifact is used. You can define the specific terms and conditions under which others can access, modify, distribute, or derive works from your artifact. This helps ensure that your intentions for the artifact are respected and that it is used in a manner consistent with your values and goals.
- c) **Attribution:** By licensing your artifact, you can require proper attribution. This means that anyone using your work must give you appropriate credit as the original creator. Attribution is important for recognition, establishing your reputation, and protecting against plagiarism or misrepresentation.
- d) **Collaboration:** Licensing can facilitate collaboration and the sharing of knowledge. By choosing an open license, such as a Creative Commons license, you can enable others to use, adapt, and build upon your artifact. This fosters a collaborative environment where others can contribute, improve, and expand upon your work, leading to innovation and the development of new ideas.
- e) **Community and Impact:** Licensing your artifact openly can help build a community around your work. It allows others to engage

with and contribute to your artifact, leading to a broader impact. Openly licensed artifacts are more likely to be shared, promoted, and integrated into educational, research, or creative projects, increasing their visibility and reach.

- f) **Legal Clarity:** Licensing provides clarity to both you and users of your artifact. By clearly defining the permissions and restrictions in a license, you reduce ambiguity and potential legal disputes. Users will have a clear understanding of what they can and cannot do with your artifact, minimizing the risk of unintentional infringement or misuse.
- g) **Ethical Considerations:** Licensing your artifact can align with ethical considerations such as open access, knowledge sharing, and the democratization of information. By making your work more accessible and available for others to use, you contribute to a culture of openness, collaboration, and the free exchange of ideas.

(Question) Where should I store licence information of my artefact?

(Answer) Regardless of where you store the license information, it is crucial to make it easily accessible and clearly visible to users of your artifact. Including the license text, instructions for compliance, and any additional relevant information will help ensure that others understand the terms under which they can use and share your artifact.

Suitable places could be metadata ([OEMetadata](#)), in a licence file or along with the artefacts' documentation.

(Question) Are licences for software, media content and X the same?

(Answer) Licenses for software and media content share some similarities but also have distinct characteristics due to the different nature of the assets being licensed. Here are some key differences between licenses for software and media content:

Purpose and Functionality: Software licenses primarily govern the use, distribution, and modification of computer software. They focus on the functionality and technical aspects of the software, such as its source code, executable files, and associated documentation. Media content licenses, on the other hand, typically address the use, distribution, and modification of creative works like images, music, videos, or written content.

Intellectual Property Considerations: Both software and media content licenses address intellectual property rights, but the specific considerations differ. Software licenses often deal with issues related to copyright, patent, and trade secrets, particularly in the case of proprietary software. Media content licenses primarily focus on copyright, as creators hold copyright over their original works, and licenses govern how others can use, distribute, and modify those works.

Openness and Collaboration: Open-source software licenses promote openness, collaboration, and sharing. They often grant users extensive rights to use, modify, distribute, and redistribute the software. Media content licenses, while they can be open licenses, may have different goals and restrictions. For example, Creative Commons licenses commonly used for media content may allow sharing and modification but with certain conditions, such as attribution or non-commercial use.

Compliance and Enforcement: Ensuring compliance with software licenses often involves adherence to specific conditions, such as including license notices, retaining copyright statements, or providing access to the source code. Violating software licenses can result in legal consequences, including infringement claims. Media content licenses typically require attribution and may restrict commercial use or derivative works, and non-compliance may also lead to legal consequences, including copyright infringement claims.

Industry-Specific Considerations: Software licenses often have industry-specific provisions and considerations. For example, software licenses may address liability limitations, warranty disclaimers, or restrictions on reverse engineering. Media content licenses may have provisions related to performance rights, synchronization rights for music in audiovisual works, or licensing for specific platforms or mediums.

While there are differences between software and media content licenses, both aim to establish legal frameworks for the use, distribution, and modification of creative assets. It's important to choose the appropriate license for the specific type of asset to ensure that the license aligns with the intended use and goals for sharing and collaboration.

(Question) **Which licence should I choose?**

(Answer) The choice of license depends on your specific goals, intentions, and the desired level of openness and control you want to maintain over your artifact. Check the section [licence types](#) for more details.

(Question) **What licence information is necessary to provide legal compliance?**

(Answer) To ensure legal compliance when providing license information, it is important to include certain key details. While the specific requirements may vary depending on the license and jurisdiction, here are some essential elements to consider:

License Name: Clearly state the name of the license that applies to your artifact. This helps users identify the specific terms and conditions under which they can use and share your work.

License Text: Provide the full text of the license, either within the artifact itself, in a separate license file, or through a link to the license text.

Including the complete license text ensures that users have access to the license terms and can review them in detail.

Attribution Requirements: If the license includes attribution requirements, specify how attribution should be given. This typically involves mentioning the original creator’s name, copyright notice, and any other relevant information as per the requirements of the license.

Check [attribution](#) for more information.

Redistribution Guidelines: If the license permits redistribution or sharing of the artifact, outline any specific guidelines or conditions that should be followed. This can include instructions for including the license text, copyright notices, or other information when redistributing the artifact.

Modification Guidelines: If the license allows modification or adaptation of the artifact, clarify any obligations or requirements related to derivative works. For example, some licenses may require that modified versions be released under the same or a compatible license.

Disclaimer or Warranty Statements: Depending on the license, it may be necessary to include disclaimers or warranty statements to clarify that the artifact is provided ”as is” without any warranties or guarantees. This helps protect you, as the licensor, from potential liability.

Contact Information: Provide a way for users to contact you if they have questions or need further clarification regarding the license or the artifact itself. This can be an email address, a website, or other appropriate contact details.

Additionally, it’s a good practice to make the license information easily accessible and clearly visible to users, either within the artifact or through accompanying documentation or a project website.

7.2 Intermediate

(Question) **How to handle sources with no licence information?**

(Answer) When you come across sources that have no license information, it’s important to exercise caution and consider the following steps:

Seek Permission: If you want to use or incorporate a source without license information into your own work, try to contact the original creator or rights holder to request permission. Reach out through appropriate channels, such as email, website contact forms, or social media, and clearly explain your intentions and how you plan to use the source. Respect their response, whether it’s granting permission, denying permission, or requesting further information.

Look for Copyright Information: Even if there is no explicit license mentioned, the work may still be protected by copyright. Look for any indications of copyright ownership, such as the creator’s name, copyright symbol (©), or copyright year. In the absence of license information,

it's safest to assume that the work is protected by copyright and seek permission from the copyright holder.

Public Domain or Openly Licensed Material: Consider whether the work may fall under public domain or an openly licensed category. Public domain refers to works that are not protected by copyright, either due to expiration, waiver, or inapplicability. Openly licensed material, such as Creative Commons-licensed works, may allow certain permissions for use. Conduct research or utilize public domain and openly licensed repositories to find suitable content that aligns with your needs.

Fair Use or Fair Dealing: Depending on your jurisdiction, you may have provisions for fair use (in the United States) or fair dealing (in some other countries). These legal doctrines allow for limited use of copyrighted material without permission, under specific circumstances such as criticism, commentary, or educational purposes. However, the application of fair use or fair dealing can be complex and context-specific, so it's advisable to consult legal counsel or seek guidance from authoritative sources in your jurisdiction.

Find Alternative Sources: If you are unable to obtain permission or determine the licensing status of a particular source, consider finding alternative sources that have clear license information. There are many repositories, platforms, and websites that provide openly licensed or public domain content that can be used more confidently.

It is crucial to respect copyright and intellectual property rights when using or incorporating the work of others into your own projects. When in doubt about the license status or permissions for a particular source, it's best to be on the side of caution and seek proper authorization or find alternative content with clear licensing information.

(Question) How to handle data bases with no licence information?

(Answer) Contact the Database Owner: Try to identify and contact the owner or administrator of the database. Reach out to them through appropriate channels, such as email or website contact forms, and inquire about the licensing terms or permissions for using the data. Respect their response, whether it's providing the license information, granting permission, or requesting further clarification.

Check for Terms of Use or Terms of Service: Even if there is no explicit license mentioned, the database may have associated terms of use or terms of service. Look for a "Terms of Use" or "Legal" section on the database website or search for any accompanying documentation. These terms may outline the permissions and restrictions for using the data.

Research Copyright Status: Consider whether the data contained in the database is subject to copyright protection. In some cases, the database may consist of factual or non-original data that is not eligible for copyright protection. However, if the database includes creative elements or

substantial selection, arrangement, or originality, copyright may apply. Conduct research or seek legal advice to determine the copyright status of the database.

Consult Legal Experts: If you're dealing with critical or sensitive data, it's advisable to consult legal experts, such as intellectual property attorneys or data privacy specialists. They can help analyze the situation, assess the legal implications, and provide guidance on the proper use and handling of the database.

Explore Open Data Initiatives: Consider utilizing openly licensed or public domain databases that are explicitly designed for open access and use. There are numerous open data initiatives and repositories available that provide data under clear licensing terms, such as Open Data Commons or government open data portals.

Ethical Considerations: Even if there are no clear license terms, it's important to consider ethical considerations when using databases. Respect the privacy rights and data protection regulations that may apply to the data within the database. Ensure that you handle the data responsibly and in compliance with applicable laws and regulations.

Remember, the absence of license information can create uncertainty regarding the proper use and handling of databases. Whenever possible, seek authorization or [clarification](#) from the database owner or consult legal experts to ensure compliance with relevant legal and ethical considerations.

7.3 Advanced

(Question) **How to handle artefacts comprised of various licences?**

(Answer) Handling artifacts with various licenses requires careful attention to detail, documentation, and compliance with each individual license's terms. By understanding the licenses, separating components when necessary, and clearly communicating the license information, you can navigate the complexities and ensure legal compliance.

The manual process is partially automatised within [dalicc](#).

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